

ARTS

THE MEMORY OF THE RUINS IN CULTURAL EXPERIENCE

Masliakova A.

Ph.D. in Art Criticism

Galway University

Abstract

It is a well-known fact that ruins have been playing a significant part in our lives. We are surrounded by ruins, and yet we know so little about their past, their memories. And it seems to me that it is about time we listened to their stories and tried to unveil the truth about them.

Keywords: Ruins, memory, cultural experience, destruction, preservation.

As we all know, the present situation in Europe and in the Whole World obviously represents a challenge to our ability for rethinking the connection between Art History, Travelling and Memory, not only due to the new conscience spreading in our minds that traditional methods on which we have relied for centuries have lost their actuality, but also due to the fact that the whole idea of travelling since those times has been in many cases based on entertainment. That is to say, unfortunately, the majority of tourists seems to be more interested in buying souvenirs and taking photos than in the exploration of the multilayered history of humanity expressed in Art from Antiquity to the Present day. And yet, the Idea of Memory seems to be of vital importance nowadays. Suffice it to mention that one of the main objectives of the Memory of the World Program initiated by UNESCO is “to increase awareness worldwide of the existence and significance of documentary heritage” [1].

Regrettably, there has been a disturbing trend to Erase the Memory of the specific events, in other words, many people have been “airbrushed” from the history, exiled and executed, as shown by Aomar Boum in his book “Memories of Absence: How Muslims Remember Jews in Morocco” shining light on the history of the Jews who neighbored the Muslims in Morocco until their exodus in 1963, Stuart Rosenberg’s film “Voyage of the Damned” based on actual events concerning the fate of the ocean liner St. Louis carrying Jewish refugees from Germany to Cuba in 1939, Daniel Libeskind’s “Voids” – empty spaces cut through the building of the Jewish Museum in Berlin from the basement to the roof addressing the physical emptiness resulting from the Holocaust, etc. A lot of the objects of Art have been banned, removed from public view or even destroyed. In this case one should mention Tutankhamun’s tomb comprising redesigned Art objects originally belonging to either Akhenaten or Nefertiti; the city of Carthage that was annihilated by the Romans in 146 B.C.; Iconoclasts who called for the removal or destruction of icons, Savonarola who made Botticelli burn his paintings and the Nazi book burnings; the churches and other buildings destroyed during the Soviet regime (e.g. the Königsberg Castle which was blown up in 1967; ironically, the unfinished building of the House of Soviets, standing on the site of the Castle’s moat, is also about to be razed to the ground due to its

poor condition [2]); the Tuileries Palace that was demolished during the Paris Commune and the statues of twenty-eight Kings of Judah decorating the west façade of Notre-Dame de Paris that were pulled down and decapitated during the French Revolution [3]; the Degenerate Art Exhibition aiming to ridicule and diminish the value of the Modern Art; the objects of Art that were removed from Germany after World War II and kept in secret storage at the Hermitage Museum for many years; the collection of Hildebrand Gurlitt, comprising the Artworks looted by the Nazi, which remained unknown until 2013 [4]; a great number of performances by Russian artists that were cancelled worldwide at the outbreak of the War in Ukraine in 2022 (including bans on performances of Pyotr Ilyich Tchaikovsky’s music [5]); an exhibition “Rejected Masterpieces. The Challenge of Pavel Tretyakov”, which was held at the Tretyakov Gallery in Moscow, telling a story of a Russian businessman and patron of Art who fearlessly bought “controversial” Artworks such as “Ivan the Terrible Killing His Son” by Ilya Repin and Vasily Surikov’s “Boyarina Morozova”, “The Swirl” by Filipp Malyavin, etc. And Jean-Paul Sartre says in his book “Being and Nothingness” that “non-being always appears within the limits of a human expectation”, and “man is the only being by whom a destruction can be accomplished”, i.e. “a being is fragile if it carries in its being a definite possibility of non-being”; that is to say, “destruction supposes a pre-judicative comprehension of nothingness as such and a conduct in the face of nothingness”, and it is a human being who “apprehends one being as destructible” [6].

Indeed, it is appalling to observe the lists of the Artworks that have been damaged through our fault – a guard of the Museo Archeologico in Florence smashed the famous François Vase into 638 pieces, mentally disturbed geologist attacked “The Pieta” by Michelangelo with a hammer, one of the visitors of the Hermitage Museum sprayed Rembrandt’s “Danaë” with sulphuric acid and cut it twice with a knife, an American art dealer Tony Shafrazi sprayed the words “Kill All Lies” on Picasso’s “Guernica”, Alexander Brener, a Russian-Jewish painter from Moscow, defaced “The White Cross” by Kazimir Malevich with a dollar symbol with two vertical lines against the entire width and height of the famous canvas with a canister of green aerosol

paint, a Chilean student Luis Onfray tried to steal Rodin's "The Torso of Adèle" from the Chilean National Museum of Fine Arts considering the theft of the statue as a performance making a statement about Art and its value [7], etc. Without any doubt, there is a thin line between destruction and Art making process (see the examples below), yet it seems to me that one's desperate attempts to attract people's attention by damaging (and / or stealing) priceless Works of Art belonging to all humankind and forming the basis of our cultural identity have nothing to do with Performance Art whatsoever. I remember discussing this issue with my mother, and she said that it might be that the reason behind all this is that the great masterpieces are "achingly beautiful", they are too powerful, and some persons simply cannot bear to see (or listen to) them. Suffice it to recall Naval Lapid's film "Synonyms" depicting a young Israel man named Yoav who, walking past the

Notre-Dame de Paris, repeats to himself "Don't look up" rejecting the beauty before him; and at the end of the film he shoots at the tower of the Notre-Dame with an imaginary machine-gun as if anticipating the fire of 2019 causing extensive damage to the cathedral. Not long ago, I came across Nikolay Tsiskaridze's interview on Art in general and Michelangelo's "David" in particular in which he says that he finds it extremely difficult to take his eyes off the original sculpture of "David" located at the Gallery of the Academy in Florence; and he also is of the view that Beauty Can Kill. I suppose that all of us have been overstimulated by Art at least once and have had this feeling that we need to close our eyes, turn away and have a little break from it. And I reckon that, perhaps, this is one of the best solutions to the problem mentioned above, apart from protecting the Works of Art by bulletproof acrylic glass panels.

Fig.1. The ruins of the Königsberg Cathedral

Fortunately, considerable efforts have been made to preserve the Memory of the Past for the Future, starting with Aleksandr Solzhenitsyn's "Archipelag GULag" revealing the truth about political repressions in SSSR and ending with an exhibition "Sunken Cities: Egypt's Lost Worlds" featuring ancient Art objects which were recovered from the seabed and put on public view at the British Museum in London in 2016. Let alone the so-called Monuments Men and Women – curators and professors who managed to find thousands of the masterworks stolen by the Nazis and return them to their rightful owners, including the famous Ghent Altarpiece. A great number of the Artworks has been restored using the old black and white photos, the drawings and the paintings depicting those masterpieces as a guide (The Gatchina Palace, The Amber Room in Pushkin, The Cathedral of Christ the Savior in Moscow, Dresden's Old Town, etc.). More often than not, when cleaning the paintings and removing centuries of grime and dust from them, as well as the corrections and glues applied during previous restoration campaigns, they tend to leave certain small areas unrestored so that visitors

could see the original version of the Artwork in question, and, at the same time, go "back to the future" and compare it with the later additions. And it is interesting to note that while rebuilding the ruined Dresden Frauenkirche, they reused lots of stones salvaged from the original church and thus incorporated the "fragments" of the Memory of the Past into the "framework" of the Present. By the way, most of the old buildings in Germany, including the Frauenkirche, were built of sandstone which, as we all know, tends to change its color and darken over time due to absorption of water vapour from the air; and when I visited Dresden in 2014, the contrast between the old and the new sandstone still could be seen ensuring that the sad fate suffered by the church was not forgotten.

On the one hand, I share the opinion of an American Art historian Vincent Scully who in one of his lectures on Modern Architecture says that "the ruin is deeply built into the culture of the Modern Age" for one of the great facts of the 20th century is that "it made more ruins than any other century ever did before"; and since, for instance, La Sagrada Família always was a

great ruin and had an enormous appeal “as a never to be finished ruin”, it might have been better to leave everything as it was and not to try to complete Antoni Gaudí’s project [8]. I must say that such a Romantic perception of the ruins has been quite common among many artists and writers, so much so that there was a time when Europe was literally obsessed with fake dilapidated buildings, or “ruin follies”, creating a false impression of a history that never happened (the Jealous Wall in Westmeath, the Ruin Bridge in the landscape park of Alexandria, the Apollo Colonnade in Pavlovsk, Hubert Robert’s capricci decorating in the White Hall of the Whiter Palace in St. Petersburg, etc.). And incidentally, Albert Speer, whose attitude towards ruins was rather different from “the melancholic view of the unstable future in Robert and Soane’s pictures”, developed his own “theory of ruin value” (Ruinenwerttheorie) according to which the Third Reich’s architecture should be erected in such a way that it would not be inferior to the ruins of Greek and Roman monuments even after hundreds or thousands of years [9]. In an ironic twist of fate, his monumental buildings were destroyed only a decade after he imagined his “eternal ruin” (except for the four entrance pavilions and underpasses leading to the Victory Column and the Schwerbelastungskörper – a hefty concrete cylinder constructed for the purpose of testing the load-bearing capacity of the ground on the planned site of Hitler’s Triumphal Arch). And I suppose that, when considering such issues, one can never be too careful for, more often than not, “the romance of the ruin” gives way to “the terror of the ruin”, “the sorrow of the ruin”, and “the drama of the ruin”; and I quite agree with Zoltán Somhegyi who in his book called “Reviewing the Past: The Presence of Ruins” says that “although ruins are now ruins, through their survival, however fragmented, they may represent a serious challenge to the representatives of the new ideology, who do not wish to retain, let alone actively maintain, the reminders of the past” [10]. “Ruins are powerful, but they cannot defend themselves, neither against Nature, nor against man, who sometimes wishes to accelerate the work of Nature” (let us mention in this regard the Lower Dacha of the Emperor Nicholas II in Peterhof which remains in ruins to this day), hence it is the duty of those who understand the importance of Cultural Heritage to protect those ruins as well as all kinds of precious memories “dwelling” there.

Some of the historic ruins have been left intact, more or less (for instance, The Kaiser Wilhelm Memorial Church in Berlin), and if you look closely, you may be able to see the traces of shell splinters on the western columns of St. Isaac’s Cathedral in St. Petersburg reminding of the horrors of World War II. Not to mention the fact that there has been a tendency to see the act of destruction (real or imaginary) as a part of the Art making process adding new meanings to the very notion of the Artwork and leading to the transformation of the nature of the dialogue between the viewer (and / or listener) and the object of Art – one need only mention Lucio Fontana’s stabbed and slashed canvases; Banksy’s “Girl with Balloon” self-destructed right after the auction in 2018; Antoni Gaudí’s famous mosaics

made of broken tiles, plates and cups; Thomas Hirschhorn’s installation “Abschlag” featuring half-demolished apartments decorated with the paintings by the revolutionary Russian constructivists – Malevich, Kandinsky, Ekster, etc.; Damien Hirst’s “Treasures from the Wreck of the Unbelievable” plunging visitors into a fantasy universe and presenting some of the cargo of a treasure ship called “The Unbelievable” which, according to the artist, was found near Africa in 2008; “Autoxylopyrocycloboros” – Simon Starling’s partially burnt photo representing the artist’s voyage across Loch Long on a small wooden steamboat fueled by wood which was cut from the boat itself until it sank; Cornelia Parker’s “Cold Dark Matter: An Exploded View” depicting ragged fragments of a garden shed which was blown up by the British Army for the artist symbolizing transience and fragility; Marc Bauer’s drawing technique involving erasing images and integrating the traces of those deletions; Nayan Kulkarni’s dynamic installation “Hryre” (or “Ruin”) formed from fragments of medieval texts projected across the fractured stonework of St. John’s Church in Chester; deconstructivist architecture created by the incomparable Zaha Hadid breaking the rules of classical design; visual installation “La Ferita” (“The Wound”) decorating the façade of the Renaissance Palazzo Strozzi in Florence created by a French artists JR bringing Art outside and warning of the “social wound” to communities deprived of culture under the lingering Covid-19 health emergency [11]; Susan Collins’ trompe l’oeil “crack” drawn on one of the walls of Birmingham’s Ikon Gallery corresponding to Carlo Crivelli’s “Madonna and Child” hanging on the other side of the same wall and representing a dramatic crack painted into the marble; Helene Schmitz’s photography series “Living rooms” depicting her childhood home devastated after the fire; Anselm Kiefer’s exhibition “Chute d’étoiles” (“Falling stars”) presented at the Grand Palais in Paris inviting visitors into ramshackle rooms constructed amid the rubble of broken concrete slabs and crumpled sheets of corrugated iron; not to mention his post-apocalyptic paintings, exhibited at the Dodge’s Palace in Venice in 2022, beginning with a quotation from the writings of the Venetian philosopher Andrea Emo, namely: “These writings, when burned, will finally cast a little light” [12], etc. And I quite agree with Iris Murdoch who in her book “Under the Net” says that perhaps Leonardo da Vinci like nobody else understood the ephemeral nature of human existence and “deliberately made the Last Supper perishable” [13].

To sum it up, ruins surrounding us have a tremendous impact of our society forming the basis for our cultural experience. We make thousands of decisions every day, and it seems to me that our attitude towards Art and Culture is one of the main factors indicating whether or not we have made the right choice. And it seems to me that one should not pass by an Object of Art in a hurry; on the contrary, one should slow down, dive into the space-time of the Artworks surrounding him (or her), engage in a dialogue with them so as to remember how to “dwell” and thus appreciate the significance of the Idea of Memory expressed in Art, and

share this experience with other people since only together can we make this World a better place.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I would like to thank Dr. Gerald Cipriani for his help with this research.

References

1. UNESCO, "Memory of the World", accessed July 26, 2021, <https://en.unesco.org/programme/mow>.
2. "'Robot' building in Kaliningrad to be demolished next year", accessed March 19, 2022, <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2020/nov/12/robot-building-in-kaliningrad-to-be-demolished-next-year>.
3. "Missing Heads of the Kings from Notre-Dame de Paris", accessed December 13, 2021, <https://joyofmuseums.com/museums/europe/france-museums/paris-museums/musee-national-du-moyen-age/the-gallery-of-kings-heads/>.
4. "Gurlitt Case: Hildebrand Gurlitt: Allied Documents, Interrogation and Collection List 1945-1950", accessed July 27, 2021, <https://www.lootedart.com/QDES4V964951>.
5. Ivens, M, "Banning Tchaikovsky Won't Win the War in Ukraine", accessed April 27, 2022, <https://www.bloomberg.com/opinion/articles/2022-03-12/ukraine-war-cancel-culture-banning-tchaikovsky-won-t-stop-putin>.
6. Sartre, J-P, "Being and Nothingness", accessed July 28, 2021, http://www.ahandfulofleaves.org/documents/BeingAndNothingness_Sartre.pdf.
7. "Rodin stolen 'to test museum'", accessed September 18, 2021, <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2005/jun/20/arts.artsnews>.
8. Scully, V, "Art Nouveau, Gaudí, Expressionism (Modern Architecture Course)", accessed February 21, 2022, https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gOqs74F5qb4&ab_channel=VincentScullyLectures.
9. Ishida, K, "Albert Speer's 'Theory of Ruin Value'", accessed May 4, 2022, https://www.arc.ritsumei.ac.jp/download/AR_SPECIALISSUE_vol.1_5_ISHIDA.pdf.
10. Somhegyi, Z, *Reviewing the Past: The Presence of Ruins* (London: Rowan & Littlefield International Ltd, 2020, p. 200).
11. "Anselm Kiefer. Questi scritti, quando verranno bruciati, daranno finalmente un po' di luce (Andrea Emo)", accessed April 29, 2022, <https://palazzo-ducale.visitmuve.it/en/mostre-en/mostre-in-corso-en/anselm-kiefer-at-doges-palace/2022/02/22305/anselm-kiefer-exhibition/>.
12. "Artist JR shows off Italy 'museum opening' in latest work", accessed May 4, 2022, <https://www.kuwaittimes.com/artist-jr-shows-off-italy-museum-opening-in-latest-work/>.
13. Murdoch, I, *Under the Net* (London, Vintage Books, 2002, p. 61).